

Press Release #2
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COcyber launches AI Cybersecurity Deephack to tackle phishing threats across civilian and defence sectors

Online Deephack: 24–26 April 2025 | Pre-deephack webinar: 2 April 2025

Brussels, Belgium. Phishing attacks are on the rise, targeting both civil society and defence sectors across Europe. To confront this challenge, [COcyber](#) is launching the [AI Cybersecurity Deephack: Advancing European Defence Capabilities](#), an online event taking place from **24 to 26 April 2025**. The deephack brings together startups, SMEs, corporates, public-sector tech teams, cybersecurity professionals, and university students to develop **AI-powered solutions** that detect and prevent phishing attacks in real time, strengthening Europe's dual-use cybersecurity capabilities.

Participants can work with NLP, anomaly detection, and threat intelligence to design AI systems that stop phishing attacks before they strike. Solutions should be designed for deployment across both secure defence environments and civilian networks, considering real-scenario challenges such as **AI bias, latency and real-time**

decision making, potential dual-use risks, data sensitivity and resilience to adversarial AI.

The programme includes daily checkpoints, mentoring sessions, pitching training, and final presentations evaluated by an expert jury. Winning teams will receive **visibility across the COcyber ecosystem, tailored mentorship, and access to support programmes** such as the EIT Digital Speed Master course and fast-track acceleration opportunities.

Key dates

- Deadline to apply: 13 April 2025
- Online onboarding: 22 April 2025
- Deephack: 24–26 April 2025

In the words of Alessandra Zini from the COcyber project lead, [EIT Digital](#): “Europe’s capacity to effectively and swiftly respond to ever-evolving external threats must leverage the power of research and innovation for dual-use cybersecurity applications. With this deephack, we’re scouting forward-looking minds - startups, students, researchers - capable of building adaptable solutions that strengthen both civilian and defence resilience, and contribute to the EU’s strategic security autonomy - which is currently a major focus of funding.”

Pre-deephack webinar: 2 April | 15:00 CET | Zoom

To support prospective applicants and confirmed participants, COcyber in collaboration with [Ultrahack](#) will host a [pre-deephack webinar](#) on April 2nd. This online session will **introduce the deephack scope, explain practical and technical expectations**, and provide participants with the opportunity to meet the organising team and partners. Whether participants are already registered or still considering applying, the webinar will offer guidance to navigate the challenge and its dual-use dimension.

Interested participants are encouraged to [apply now](#) and [register for the pre-deephack webinar](#) to secure their spot and prepare for the challenge.

About COcyber: [COcyber](#) is an ambitious two-year EU-funded initiative launched in July 2024 to strengthen exchange, coordination, and collaboration between civilian and defence cybersecurity communities across Europe. Led by EIT Digital and involving nine European organisations, the project will deliver practical tools, policy frameworks, and a trusted online platform to bridge the gap between sectors and support a unified response to evolving cyber threats.

Follow COcyber on [LinkedIn](#) and [Bluesky](#) - stay tuned for further developments in this collaborative ecosystem!

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